

**Recommendation from the
Director of the Office for Risk
Assessment and Research to the
Minister of Welfare, Health and
Sport (VWS), and the Minister for
Agriculture**

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**Recommendation on the risks of tuberculosis and
cysticercosis in veal calves in the event of changes
in inspection policy**

The causative agents of tuberculosis in cattle, the bacterium *Mycobacterium bovis* and the tapeworm *Taenia saginata*, can be transmitted from cattle to humans (zoonoses). Amongst others, meat inspections are intended to identify animals that carry such pathogens. The inspection procedures are described in considerable detail in Regulation EC no. 854/2004. Within the framework of risk-based inspection policy it is pertinent to ask to what extent inspection procedures designed to detect the above-mentioned pathogens in veal calves, still contribute to reducing the risks to public and animal health.

The Chief Inspector of the Veterinary and Import Division (V&I) of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) asked the Office for Risk Assessment (BuRO) to assess the risks of tuberculosis and cysticercosis in veal calves if certain inspection procedures, designed to detect the aforementioned zoonoses, were omitted, or were carried out differently.

Conclusions

The risk of tuberculosis is extremely low in the case of both white and rose veal calves born and fattened in officially tuberculosis free (OTF) EU Member States such as the Netherlands, and originating from non-suspect herds. In terms of animal and public health monitoring it would make no difference if, in these calves, an incision of the mediastinal lymph nodes and a transverse incision of the lungs were omitted, provided that other procedures to detect tuberculosis were carried out in accordance with the requirements.

However, there would be a risk if the above procedures were omitted in the case of calves born or fattened in non-OFT EU Member States. This applies particularly to rose veal (category Z) calves, and sometimes also to white veal (category V) calves. In view of the severity of tuberculosis (TB) in humans, it is advisable to make full use of the detection options for TB in the post-mortem inspection of these calves.

For TB detection there is no added value in splitting the vertebral column prior to the post-mortem inspection of veal calves, if they exhibited no abnormality during the ante-mortem inspection which could indicate tuberculosis of the spine.

In recent years very few cases of cysticercosis have been found in veal calves slaughtered in the Netherlands (less than 2 in 100,000 calves). However, one must consider here that the current PM inspection is particularly insensitive on this point: at least 80% of cysticercosis cases go undetected. The masseters are cited as the preferential site, but in the case of natural infection less than 2% of the cysticerci are present in these muscles. There is therefore practically nothing to be gained by making several incisions in the masseters. The chance of detection would probably be increased by serological screening and incision of skeletal muscles. However, one should consider whether the cost of such screening would be justified in view of the incidence of cysticercosis in veal calves and the low risks of the disease (tapeworm) in humans.

Recommendation

The Ministers of Welfare, Health and Sport (VWS), Economic Affairs (EZ) and Social Affairs and Employment (SZW)

- There would be no increased risk of bovine tuberculosis as a result of the proposed changes in the post-mortem inspection of veal calves born and fattened in officially tuberculosis free Member States. In respect of all other veal calves the risk would be increased.
- There would be no increased risk of cysticercosis as a result of the proposed changes in the post-mortem inspection, irrespective of the origin of the calves.
- When slaughtering animals from herds in which tuberculosis has been identified, staff should wear an FFP3 face mask for personal protection.

Inspector General of the NVWA

- The omission of an incision of the mediastinal lymph nodes and the transverse incision of the lungs during post-mortem inspection would not increase the risk of bovine tuberculosis in veal calves born and fattened in officially tuberculosis free Member States.
- In all other veal calves there would be some increased risk if the above procedures were omitted from the post-mortem inspection. Therefore all available methods of detecting *M. bovis* in these slaughter animals should be used.

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- For the detection of *M. bovis* in veal calves, there is no added value in splitting the vertebral column prior to post-mortem inspection.
- If the incisions of the masseters were limited to one incision on either side of the outermost or innermost masseters, and if the tongue, including part of the tonsils, were freed prior to the post-mortem inspection, this would not lead to an increased risk of cysticercus bovis.
- If a carcass with cysticerci or tuberculous lesions is found in a slaughter batch of veal calves, all carcasses and organs from that batch must be subjected to intensive post-mortem inspection.
- Decision-making on the recommended changes in inspection policy on veal calves should be postponed until after the anticipated publication of the EFSA's opinion on cattle in mid-2013.

Yours faithfully

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Investigation into the risks of tuberculosis and cysticercosis in veal calves in the event of changes in inspection policy

Background

Around 1.5 million veal calves are slaughtered every year in the Netherlands. These include white¹ and rose² veal calves. In 2012 the NVWA made an inventory of the various procedures involved in the inspection of veal calves and how they were implemented. Based on this inventory, proposals were made for a risk-based unification of the post-mortem (PM) inspection, and the presentation of carcasses and organs for inspection.

The proposals were submitted to the management team of the Veterinary and Import Division (V&I) of the NVWA. The management team largely approved the proposed changes, provided that the Office for Risk Assessment and Research (BuRO) carried out an assessment of the risks of a number of specified changes.

These are the risks of *Mycobacterium (M.) bovis* and *Taenia saginata* cysticercus (cysticercus bovis) in veal calves in the event of amended policy on splitting the spinal column, incisions of the mediastinal lymph nodes, a transverse incision of the lungs, freeing the tongue together with part of the tonsils, and incisions of the masseters.

The questions asked

In the light of these developments the Director of the Veterinary and Import Division (V&I) of the NVWA submitted the following questions to BuRO:

"In comparison with the methodology described in EC Regulation 854/2004, is there an increased risk of M. bovis if calves under 13 months old are also presented for PM inspection without first being split, if the mediastinal lymph nodes are only incised if there are visible abnormalities, and if the transverse incision of the posterior third of the lungs is omitted?"

"In comparison with the methodology described in EC Regulation 854/2004, is there an increased risk of cysticercus bovis in this category of veal calves if only the external masseters are incised, once on either side, and the tongue including part of the tonsils is freed and presented for inspection wholly or partly separate from the head?"

¹ Calves up to 8 months (since 1-7-2008 referred to in European legislation as 'Category V calves')

² Calves from 8 months to a year (since 1-7-2008 referred to in European legislation as 'Category Z calves').

Approach

Insight into the context of the research question was obtained from the NVWA's internal report containing an inventory of differences in procedure in veal calf slaughterhouses and proposals for uniform presentation of carcasses and organs and uniform implementation of the post-mortem inspection, and the decision sheet (Besluitenblad) of 5 July 2012 drawn up by management team of the Veterinary and Import Division (V&I). Requests for further information or clarification were answered by V&I staff, after which the risks of a change in monitoring policy were assessed. The resulting recommendation underwent an external peer review by various experts from the University of Utrecht and an internal review by various uninvolved colleagues at BuRO. It was coordinated with the V&I and the relevant policy departments of the Ministries concerned (EZ and VWS).

Risk assessment

Risks and the nature of the risks

The inspection of slaughter animals, including veal calves, is intended to detect in good time any abnormalities that could be linked to the presence of pathogens or undesirable substances, and so to control risks to the safety of products of animal origin. The Food Chain Information system (VKI), and ante-mortem (AM) and post-mortem (PM) inspections are part of this in-process control. Often lesions that could indicate zoonoses can only be detected at the PM inspection and only in those cases where there are visible or palpable abnormalities. The inspection rules, based on Section IV of the European Hygiene Regulation (854/2004), describe in detail the procedures to be carried out during the inspection [1]. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) is expected to publish an opinion in mid-2013 on post-mortem examination of production animals, including bovine animals such as veal calves.

The agents that cause tuberculosis (*M.bovis*) and cysticercosis (*cysticercus bovis*) present significant risks to public health. The corresponding animal diseases can be detected during the inspection by palpation or visual inspection [2]. Certain tissues are incised to detect as far as possible any *M. bovis* and *cysticercus bovis* infections. Within the framework of risk-based inspection policy it is pertinent to ask whether the likelihood of discovering these particular pathogens during the inspection justifies the cost of specific inspection procedures.

M. bovis - part of the Mycobacterium Tuberculosis Complex - is the pathogen responsible for bovine tuberculosis. Bovine tuberculosis is a zoonosis (transmissible to humans), and exposure to *M. bovis* in humans can lead to the lesions typically associated with tuberculosis. Human infection is usually caused by drinking inadequately heated milk contaminated with *M. bovis* or consuming dairy products made from it. A tuberculosis infection can be contracted through contact with infected animals, due to breathing in contaminated aerosols [3].

Consumers can be infected by the tapeworm *Taenia (T.) saginata* by eating unheated or inadequately heated beef contaminated with *cysticercus bovis*. If the parasite is present in the meat, it can develop into a full-grown tapeworm in the intestinal tract of the consumer. Tapeworm eggs excreted with the faeces, if ingested by ruminants, can again develop into cysticerci in muscle meat with infectious *cysticercus bovis* (cysticercosis).

The public health risk associated with *M. bovis* or *cysticercus bovis* in veal calves is determined by exposure to these pathogens, the likelihood of an infection and the severity of the infection concerned.

Exposure to *M. bovis* via veal calves or veal

The likelihood of *M. bovis* in veal calves very much depends on the presence of the bacterium in the site where the calves are born and raised. In countries that are officially free of *M. bovis* (officially tuberculosis-free or OTF states), the risk of infection under the current surveillance regime is extremely low. This is not the case in England, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Greece, Spain, Portugal and large parts of Italy [4]. In 2011 the import of Irish calves led to an outbreak of bovine TB in the Netherlands.

Therefore the risk of *M. bovis* being present in veal calves, brought in from non-OTF states and slaughtered in the Netherlands, cannot be regarded as negligible. This applies to both white (V) and rose (Z) veal calves. The risk of abattoir employees being exposed to *M. bovis* is extremely low in the case of veal calves from the non-OTF states referred to above, and it is unnecessary to take extra measures for personal protection when slaughtering such animals. However, extra protection is required when slaughtering veal calves from herds in which tuberculosis has been identified. In that case a mask should be worn to cover the nose and mouth.

Consumers may be exposed to *M. bovis* by consuming products from infected animals that were not detected during inspection. In the case of veal calves presenting no macroscopic abnormalities that could indicate tuberculosis, the routine incision of the lymph nodes in the lung is the most efficient method of detecting an infection. The Hygiene Regulation refers in this context to the retropharyngeal, portal and mesenterial lymph nodes [5] as well as the bronchial and mediastinal lymph nodes, which are primarily intended for detection of aerogenous infections.

Abnormalities in the mesenterial lymph nodes can be expected if oral ingestion of *M. bovis* is a significant infection route. Experimental research on calves however shows that inhalation of contaminated aerosols is by far the most significant transmission route for *M. bovis*. The macroscopically perceptible abnormalities are generally restricted to the respiratory tract and associated lymph nodes. The greatest numbers of bacteria are found in the caudal mesenterial lymph nodes [3]. This clinical picture was also seen in deer that had come into contact with other deer with intratonsillar infections.

Lesions in these animals were seen mainly in the lungs, the tracheobronchial and the medial, retropharyngeal lymph nodes and to a far lesser extent in the abdominal organs and associated lymph nodes [6]. Furthermore experiments show that an oral infection only takes hold where there are relatively high numbers of *M. Bovis*, while the infectious dose for an aerogenic infection is much lower [7].

Little is known about tuberculosis of the skeleton, such as the vertebral column, in slaughter animals. In all likelihood animals with spinal tuberculosis will show clinical abnormalities that would be picked up at the AM-inspection stage. Also, according to some researchers, tuberculosis of the spine occurs more frequently in humans than was previously thought. In South Africa vertebrae were affected in 16.3% of tuberculosis patients [8].

To sum up, abattoir personnel can be exposed to *M. bovis* if they come into contact with infected veal calves. This applies to calves from suspect herds and, incidentally, if the animals originated from or were fattened in countries which are not officially TB-free. The risk of exposure via aerosols or through hand-mouth contact leading to an infection is not negligible.

To reduce the risk of consumer exposure to *M. bovis*, in the veal calves referred to above, the mediastinal as well as the bronchial lymph nodes must be incised. Splitting the vertebral column and the incision of other lymph nodes has little or no added value in the detection of tuberculosis. If a carcass in a slaughter batch is found to have TB-type lesions, that is sufficient reason to subject the entire batch to intensive inspection.

Exposure to *C. bovis* via veal calves or veal

The source of infection in animals is the eggs of *T. saginata*, which can be excreted by humans. A tapeworm carrier can contaminate the environment with over six million eggs per day. It is estimated that 2% of Europeans are carriers of this tapeworm [2]. Animals that ingest the tapeworm eggs can, as intermediate hosts, develop cysticercosis, allowing the larval stages of the tapeworm (metacestodes) to nestle in various sites in the body. The metacestodes have a clear predilection for muscle tissue [9]. Consequently, in addition to inspection of the carcass and organs, various muscles, including the masseters, must be incised so that potential cases of cysticercosis do not escape notice.

Despite the prescribed incisions of muscle tissue to detect cysticercus bovis, the sensitivity of the current PM inspection is very low [10]. The percentages reported in the literature vary on this point from 80% [11] to over 99% missed diagnoses [12]. The percentage of missed diagnoses is only supposed to be able to fall to around 20% in the case of high-grade infections [9], but even in those cases only 3% of over 2300 cysticerci present or were found during the routine inspection [13].

The available data on the prevalence of cysticercus bovis are based on abattoir data and, for the reasons indicated, are a substantial underestimate of the actual prevalence.

In 2010 only Lithuania and Sweden reported the results of monitoring for cysticercosis. In both Lithuania and Sweden no cases of cysticercosis were detected in 41,194 and 451,125 bovine animals respectively [4]. In the nineteen eighties the prevalence of cysticercosis in cattle in the Netherlands was around 2% [14]. By 2011 it had decreased by a factor of ten and *C. bovis* was only found in 0.3% of cattle.

The prevalence in veal calves in 2011 was of a lower order of magnitude: suspected cysticercus bovis lesions were found in only 0.002% (1.7 per 100,000) of slaughtered veal calves [15,16]. The majority of the lesions are found in the musculature of the extremities and the heart. At the stated prevalences it must be considered that around half of the cysticerci do not contain any infectious cysticercus bovis [17,18,19].

In naturally infected animals, in which all musculature was incised at several sites, 1.5% of the total number of cysticerci were found in the *Mm. masseter* and *pterygoideus*. By contrast, no cysticerci were found in the masseters using the incisions prescribed for the conventional PM inspection: they were only found in the heart, the *Triceps brachii*, and the tongue [17]. In artificially infected animals only 4% of the total number of cysticerci were found in the masseters once these had been cut into 0.5 cm sections [20]. At the current prevalence of suspect lesions the incisions of the masseters contribute extremely little to the detection of cysticercus bovis. Incisions of the more significant preferential sites such as skeletal muscles of the extremities and the heart are more effective in controlling the risks of cysticercus bovis, particularly if combined with serological diagnostics.

To sum up: at the current prevalence of cysticercus bovis in veal calves slaughtered in the Netherlands, if the incisions of the masseters were limited to just one incision of the innermost or outermost masseters on each side, the likelihood of detecting cysticercus bovis would be only negligibly reduced. The same applies if the tongue and (part of) the tonsils were freed prior to the PM inspection and presented for inspection separate from the carcass. The increase in the risk of cysticercus bovis to consumers caused by the above changes in inspection policy is negligible. Cysticercosis will usually manifest itself as a herd problem. Therefore, if a single calf with cysticercosis is observed in the slaughter line, that is sufficient reason to subject the whole batch to intensive inspection.

Severity of infection with *M. bovis* or cysticercus bovis

An *M. bovis* infection is usually contracted by consuming contaminated raw milk or products made with it, and is far less often contracted from meat. The incubation period varies from 8 weeks to a lifetime. Following infection around 10% of people develop the illness. The symptoms are not very specific and consist of fever, fatigue and emaciation. More specific symptoms can occur depending on the localisation of tuberculous inflammations. This is usually in the area of the respiratory system but sometimes also of the liver or kidneys, for example. Thanks to risk-reducing measures, humans now scarcely ever contract *M. bovis*. This is in contrast to tuberculosis infection by *M. Tuberculosis*, the pathogen of which can be transmitted relatively easily between humans [21].

In contrast to *M. bovis*, *Cysticercus bovis* is mainly transmitted through consumption of contaminated, uncooked beef. One or more tapeworms (*T. saginata*) can develop in humans who have ingested infectious cysticerci. Infectious eggs of this tapeworm do not lead to cysticercosis in various tissues in humans as the final host.

By contrast, both pigs and humans can be intermediate hosts to the eggs of *T. solium*. Apart from rather vague digestive complaints and sometimes peri-anal itching, *T. saginata* causes few complaints and can be effectively treated with antiparasitics. The severity of the infection is therefore slight.

Working conditions

Health and safety legislation places *Cysticercus bovis* and *M. bovis* in hazard classes 2 and 3 respectively. For *M. bovis* this means that risk-reducing measures must be taken for employees. Doing away with specific procedures during the slaughter of animals will have no impact on abattoir employees. The risk of exposure to *M. bovis* during the slaughter of veal calves from non-suspect herds is so slight that apart from the normal hygiene measures, no extra precautions are necessary. In the case of veal calves from herds in which tuberculosis has been identified, the risk of exposure is significantly higher. During the slaughter of such animals employees must wear a protective mask covering their nose and mouth to avoid inhaling aerosols contaminated with *M. bovis*.

Conclusions: Answers to the questions

1. *"In comparison with the methodology described in EC Regulation 854/2004, is there an increased risk of M. bovis if calves under 13 months old are also presented for PM inspection without first being split, if the mediastinal lymph nodes are only incised if there are visible abnormalities, and if the transverse incision of the posterior third of the lungs is omitted?"*
 - The risk of infection with *M. bovis* is extremely low in veal calves born and fattened in officially tuberculosis free (OTF) EU Member States, and originating from non-suspect herds. In these calves there is no increase in the risk of bovine tuberculosis as a result of omitting an incision of the mediastinal lymph nodes and the transverse incision of the lungs during PM inspection.
 - Partly in view of the severity of the disease in humans, there is an increased risk in omitting the procedures referred to above in veal calves born or fattened in non-OTF Member States.
 - The splitting of the vertebral column makes no real contribution to the detection of tuberculosis. For this purpose, in addition to palpation of the lungs, incisions of the airways, the lungs and associated lymph nodes are more effective.

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- In the case of bovine tuberculosis there is a real risk that infection is present in several animals in a batch. Finding a carcass with tuberculosis therefore justifies an intensive PM inspection of all the animals in the batch concerned.
2. *"In comparison with the methodology described in EC Regulation 854/2004, is there an increased risk of cysticercus bovis in this category of veal calves if only the external masseters are incised, once on either side, and the tongue including part of the tonsils is freed and presented for inspection wholly or partly separate from the head?"*
- The annual incidence of suspect lesions of cysticercus bovis in veal calves slaughtered in the Netherlands is in the order of 0.002%. In 2011, 23 veal calves were detected with such lesions, a quarter of which were estimated to consist of infectious cysticercus bovis.
 - In the case of natural infections, less than 2% of the cysticerci are found in the masseters. The majority of the cysticerci are located in the muscles of the extremities and the heart muscle - the actual preferential sites.
 - There is no increased risk of cysticercus bovis associated with restricting incisions of the masseters to one either side in the innermost or outermost masseters or freeing the tongue and part of the tonsils prior to the PM inspection of veal calves.
 - The likelihood of detecting cysticercus bovis during PM inspection, which is currently no higher than about 20%, could be improved by serological screening and incisions of the muscles of the extremities. However, the question is whether these extra costs would be justified, considering that the lack of severity of the (tapeworm) infection in humans and the fact that it is easily treatable.
 - Cysticercosis is usually a herd problem. Therefore finding a carcass with cysticercosis justifies an intensive PM inspection of all the animals in the batch concerned.

Paraph,

Dr. Antoon Opperhuizen
Director, Office for Risk Assessment and Research

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